

Equal-Life third wave scientific papers

Project title: Early Environmental quality and life-course mental health effects

Project Number: 874724

Project Acronym: Equal-Life

Work package 10 - Deliverable D10.11

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 874724

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Project start date: Jan 1 st 2020	Duration: 60 months
Project Coördinators: Irene van Kamp (RIVM)	

WP (number and title)	WP10: Management and Dissemination
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1 Summary

This report gives an overview of the published scientific papers were published between January 1st 2023 and December 31st 2023 in the context of the Equal-Life project (*Chapter 2*) and a list of papers per work package (WP) that are in the final stages of preparation in December 2023, to be submitted early 2024 or under review (*Chapter 3*) and a list of publications aimed at the general public (*Chapter 4*) For the Equal-Life publication policy, we refer to D10.2.

2 Published papers

The following scientific papers were published between January 1st 2023 and December 31st 2023 in the context of the Equal-Life project:

Peer reviewed articles

1. Alatalo, A., de Sousa Maciel, I., Kucháriková, N., Chew, S., van Kamp, I., Foraster, M., Julvez, J. & Kanninen, K. M. (2023). The Interaction between Circulating Cell-Free Mitochondrial DNA and Inflammatory Cytokines in Predicting Human Mental Health Issue Risk in Adolescents: An Explorative Study. *Biomedicines*, 11(3), 818. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines11030818>
2. van Asten, T., Milias, V., Bozzon, A. & Psyllidis, A. (2023). “Eyes on the street”: Estimating natural surveillance along Amsterdam city streets using street-level imagery. In: Goodspeed, R., Sengupta, R., Kytta, M., & Pettit, C. (eds.) *Intelligence for Future Cities: Planning through Big Data and Urban Analytics*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, pp. 215–229. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-31746-0_12
3. Dzhambov, A.M., Lercher, P., Vincens, N., Persson Waye, K., Klatter, M., Leist, L., Lachmann, T., Schreckenber, D., Belke, C., Ristovska, G., Kanninen, K.M., Botteldooren, D., van Renterghem, T., Jeram, S., Selander, J., Arat, A., White, K., Julvez, J., Clark, C., Foraster, M. & van Kamp, I. (2023). Protective effect of restorative possibilities on cognitive function and mental health in children and adolescents: A scoping review including the role of physical activity. *Environmental Research*, Volume 233, 116452, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116452>
4. Dzhambov, A., Lercher, P., Botteldooren, D. (2023). Childhood sound disturbance and sleep problems in Alpine valleys with high levels of traffic exposures and greenspace. *Environmental Research*, volume 242, 117642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.117642>
5. Dohmen, M., Braat-Eggen, E., Kemperman, A. & Hornikx, M. (2023). The Effects of Noise on Cognitive Performance and Helplessness in Childhood: A Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(1): 288. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20010288>
6. Gudi-Mindermann, H., White, M., Roczen, J., Riedel, N., Dreger, S., Bolte, G. (2023). Integrating the social environment with an equity perspective into the exposome paradigm: A new conceptual framework of the Social Exposome. *Environmental Research*, 233, 116485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116485>
7. Heinonen-Guzejev, M., Whipp, A. M., Wang, Z., Ranjit, A., Palviainen, T., van Kamp, I., & Kaprio, J. (2023). Perceived Occupational Noise Exposure and Depression in Young Finnish Adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(6), 4850. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20064850>

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8. van Kamp, I., Persson Waye, K., Kanninen, K., Gulliver, J., Bozzon, A., Psyllidis, A., Boshuizen, H., Selander, J., van den Hazel, P., Brambilla, M., Foraster, M., Julvez, J., Klatter, M., Jeram, S., Lercher, P., Botteldooren, D., Ristovska, G., Kaprio, J., Schreckenberg, D., Hornikx, M., Fels, J., Weber, M., Braat-Eggen, E., Hartmann, J., Clark, C., Vrijkotte, T., Brown, L., Bolte, G. & Equal-Life Scientific Team (2022). Early environmental quality and life-course mental health effects: The Equal-Life project. *Environmental Epidemiology*, 6(1), e183. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EE9.000000000000183>
9. Martínez-Vilavella, G., Pujol, J., Blanco-Hinojo, L., Deus, J., Rivas, I., Persavento, C., Sunyer, J., Foraster, M. (2023). The effects of exposure to road traffic noise at school on central auditory pathway functional connectivity. *Environmental Research*, 226, 115574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.115574>.
10. Miliás, V., Sharifi Noorian, S., Bozzon, A., & Psyllidis, A. (2023). Is it safe to be attractive? Disentangling the influence of streetscape features on the perceived safety and attractiveness of city streets. In: van Oosterom, P., Ploeger, H., Mansourian, A., Scheider, S., Lemmens, R., & van Loenen, B. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 26th AGILE Conference on Geographic Information Science*. Copernicus Publications, AGILE: GIScience Series, vol. 4, 8p. <https://doi.org/10.5194/agile-giss-4-8-2023>
11. Persson Waye, K., Löve, J., Lercher, P., Dzhambov, A.M., Klatter, M., Schreckenberg, D., Belke, C., Leist, L., Ristovska, G., Jeram, S., Kanninen, K.M., Selander, J., Arat, A., Lachmann, T., Clark, C., Botteldooren, D., White, K., Julvez, J., Foraster, M., Kaprio, J., Bolte, G., Psyllidis, A., Gulliver, J., Boshuizen, H., Bozzon, A., Fels, J., Hornikx, M., van den Hazel, P., Weber, M., Brambilla, M., Braat-Eggen, E., van Kamp, I. & Vincens, N. (2023). Adopting a child perspective for exposome research on mental health and cognitive development - Conceptualisation and opportunities., *Environmental Research*, 239(1), 117279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.117279>.
12. Psyllidis, A. (2023). Designing for urban health and well-being by revisiting proximity, walkability, and accessibility. In Veddeler, C., Kuijper, J., Gath-Morad, M. & van der Wal, I. (Eds.), *Future Cities—City Futures: Emerging Urban Perspectives* (pp. 152-163). Delft: TU Delft OPEN Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.34641/mg.55>
13. de Sousa Maciel, I., Piironen, A.K., Afonin, A.M., Ivanova, M., Alatalo, A., Jadhav, K.K., Julvez, J., Foraster, M., van Kamp, I. & Kanninen, K.M. (2023). Plasma proteomics discovery of mental health risk biomarkers in adolescents. *Nature Mental Health*, 1, 596–605. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44220-023-00103-2>
14. Teeuwen, R., & Psyllidis, A. (2023). Easy as child’s play? Co-designing a network-based metric for children’s access to play space. In: Sangiambut, S. (ed.) *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Computational Urban Planning and Urban Management (CUPUM 2023)*. Montreal, Canada: McGill University. <https://osf.io/7tjzh>
15. Teeuwen, R., Psyllidis, A., & Bozzon, A. (2023). Measuring children’s and adolescents’ accessibility to greenspaces from different locations and commuting settings. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 100, 101912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2022.101912>
16. Wang, Z., Zellers, S., Whipp, A.M., Heinonen-Guzejev, M., Foraster, M., Júlvez, J., van Kamp, I. & Kaprio, J. (2023). The effect of environment on depressive symptoms in late adolescence and early adulthood: an exposome-wide association study and twin modeling. *Nature Mental Health*, 1, 751–760. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44220-023-00124-x>

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17. Wang, Z., Whipp, A., Heinonen-Guzejev, M., Foraster, M., Júlvez, J. & Kaprio, J. (2023) The association between urban land use and depressive symptoms in young adulthood: a FinnTwin12 cohort study. *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology* 2023 Dec 11. doi: 10.1038/s41370-023-00619-w.

These papers are also added to the continuous reporting module in the EC portal.

3 Papers in final stages of preparation

The following papers are in the final stages of preparation in December 2023 and will be submitted early 2024 or are currently under review.

WP1

Schreckenber et al Scoping review the impact of exposome on mental health and cognitive development in children mediated by stress

Natalia Vincens et al Scoping review the impact of exposome on mental health and cognitive function in children and adolescents mediated by sleep

Maria Klätte et al Scoping review the impact of exposome on cognition in children mediated by coping and self-regulation

Gordana Ristovska et al Scoping review the impact of exposome on mental health and cognitive function in children and adolescents: developmental perspectives

WP2

Afonin, A. M., Piironen, AK, de Sousa Maciel, I. et al., Proteomic insights into mental health status: plasma markers in young adults. *bioRxiv* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.06.07.544039>

This manuscript is in revision for the journal *Translational Psychiatry*.

Gabin Drouard, Zhiyang Wang, Aino Heikkinen, Maria Foraster, Jordi Julvez, Katja M. Kanninen, Irene van Kamp, Matti Pirinen, Miina Ollikainen, Jaakko Kaprio

Lifestyle differences between co-twins are associated with decreased similarity in their internal and external exposome profiles *medRxiv* 2023.12.12.23299868;

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.12.12.23299868>. Submitted to *Nature Human Behavior*

Gabin Drouard, Fiona A. Hagenbeek, Alyce Whipp, René Pool, Jouke Jan Hottenga, Rick Jansen, Nikki Hubers, Aleksei Afonin, BIOS Consortium, BBMRI-NL Metabolomics Consortium, Gonneke Willemsen, Eco J. C. de Geus, Samuli Ripatti, Matti Pirinen, Katja M. Kanninen, Dorret I. Boomsma, Jenny van Dongen, Jaakko Kaprio Longitudinal multi-omics study reveals common etiology underlying association between plasma proteome and BMI trajectories in adolescent and young adult twins *medRxiv* 2023.06.28.23291995; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.06.28.23291995> *BMC Medicine* (in press)

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WP3

Karin Loh, Janina Fels et al Age differences in Intentional Auditory Selective Attention Switching under Noisy Conditions and in Spatial Acoustic Setups within Preschool Children” (from WP3 of Equal-Life) to the Collection “Child and Adolescent Health” as part of the Journal “Nature

Karin Loh, Julia Seitz, Sophie Nolden, Helene Gudi-Mindermann, Maud Dohmen, Irene van Kamp, Dick Botteldooren, Maarten Hornikx, Gabriele Bolte, and Janina Fels (2023). Cognitive milestone at the age of four: Intentional switching of auditory selective attention in preschool children. [Manuscript submitted for publication in Scientific Reports].

WP4:

Maud Dohmen, Ella Braat-Eggen, Maarten Hornikx, Astrid Kemperman. Children’s exposure patterns in relation to health and wellbeing. Poster presentation during the Exposome-NL conference, paper planned in 2024.

WP5:

Teeuwen, R., Miliias, V., Bozzon, A., & Psyllidis, A. (2024, expected). How well do NDVI and OpenStreetMap data capture people’s visual perceptions of urban greenspace? Landscape and Urban Planning (revised version under review).

WP7:

Zhiyang Wang, Alyce Whipp, Marja Heinonen-Guzejev, Jaakko Kaprio. Age at separation, residential mobility, and depressive symptoms among twins in late adolescence and young adulthood: a FinnTwin12 cohort study is under review at BMC Public Health (second round of revision).

Zhiyang Wang, Gabin Drouard, Alyce M. Whipp, Marja Heinonen-Guzejev, Gabriele Bolte, Jaakko Kaprio. Association between trajectories of the neighborhood social exposome and mental health in late adolescence: a FinnTwin12 cohort study. Under review

WP8:

Sammie N. G. Jansen, Bob C. Mulder, Irene van Kamp, Sandra Boekhold, Peter van den Hazel, Marcel F. Verweij Ethics of Early Detection of Disease Risk Factors: A Scoping Review BMC Medical Ethics (under review)

4 Popular Publications

Teeuwen, R., & Psyllidis, A. (2023, May). “How to map the accessibility of urban greenspaces”. <https://www.tudelft.nl/en/2023/io/may/how-to-map-the-accessibility-of-urban-green-spaces>

Miliias, V., & Psyllidis, A. (2023, September). “New tool shows accessibility of public areas for different population groups”. <https://www.tudelft.nl/en/ide/delft-design-stories/new-tool-shows-accessibility-of-public-areas-for-different-population-groups>

Teeuwen, R., Miliias, V., & Psyllidis, A. (2023, November). “Kinderen in de openbare ruimte. Urban Analytics Lab biedt inzicht in knelpunten leefomgeving” (EN: “Children in public space. The Urban

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Analytics Lab provides insight into bottlenecks in the living environment”). *Onze Jeugd* (EN: Our Youth), November 2023 issue.

Ahrens, J. & Bolte, G. (2023). Entwicklung und Erprobung eines Instruments zur Integration einer Gesundheitsgerechtigkeitsperspektive: Anwendung auf Interventionen der Stadtplanung in Europa. IPP-Info 20.

https://www.uni-bremen.de/fileadmin/user_upload/fachbereiche/fb11/ipp/Institutsuebergreifend/Transfer/IPP-Info/IPP-Info_Ausgabe-20_Web.pdf

(No publication fee)

Hasselder, P. & Bolte, G. (2023). Mobilitätsgerechtigkeit im Kontext von Shared Mobility – Eine qualitative Analyse aus Public-Health-Perspektive. IPP-Info 20.

https://www.uni-bremen.de/fileadmin/user_upload/fachbereiche/fb11/ipp/Institutsuebergreifend/Transfer/IPP-Info/IPP-Info_Ausgabe-20_Web.pdf

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